

Peroxidases. A New Method of Estimating their Activity.

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Laccase, obtained from the sap of the lac tree, which was one of the first plant oxidising enzymes to be closely studied (Bertrand, *Compt. rend.*, 1896, 122, 1215) was shown later to act upon various phenols and to oxidise them to dark quinone-like bodies (Bertrand and Mutermilch, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1907, 21, 833). In the course of the series of careful investigations of the oxidising enzymes of such common vegetables as potatoes, beet-root and cabbage, Bach and Chodat (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1342 *et seq.*) succeeded in obtaining fairly pure specimens of these oxidising enzymes, called by them 'peroxidases' because they acted only in the presence of hydrogen peroxide, and elaborated a process for the quantitative estimation of the strengths of such enzyme preparations. It was based on the observation that pyrogallol was oxidised to purpurogallin by a peroxidase in presence of a weak solution of hydrogen peroxide. Willstätter and Stoll (*Annalen*, 1918, 416, 21; also Willstätter, *Annalen*, 1921, 422, 47; Willstätter and Pollinger, *Annalen*, 1923, 430, 269) improved Bach and Chodat's method for the estimation of peroxidases and applied it to the determination of the strength of a particularly pure specimen of this enzyme which they obtained from the horse-radish (*Radicula armoracia*). They also established a convention by which the peroxidase contents of different plants could be measured and compared in terms of their 'peroxidase numbers', *i.e.*, the number of milligrams of purpurogallin obtained from 5 c.c. of the plant sap under certain definite conditions. In the cases of plant saps containing too small a quantity of peroxidase to give a sufficient amount of purpurogallin to form a precipitate by this method, two colorimetric methods have been described, one by Willstätter and Stoll (*loc. cit.*) based on the extraction of the purpurogallin with ether and comparison of its colour with a similar ethereal solution of purpuro-

gallin used as a standard, and the other by Willstätter and Weber (*Annalen*, 1926, 449, 156) based on the oxidation of leuco-malachite green in dilute acetic acid and sodium acetate solution by the peroxidase in presence of hydrogen peroxide, and comparing the intensity of the colour developed with that of a solution of malachite green used as standard. Recently Wieland and Sutter (*Ber.*, 1928, 61, 1060), while experimenting with the oxidising enzyme present in a fungus (*Art. lactarius*), found that hydroquinone was auto-oxidised to quinone under the influence of this enzyme, the reaction being assumed to proceed according to the following equation:—

The above methods of estimating the strengths of peroxidase preparations are open to several objections, and they can be relied upon as a basis of determining only approximately the relative amounts of oxidising enzymes present in different plants. It has been stated that the enzyme itself undergoes oxidation to some extent and precipitates some insoluble matter along with the purpurogallin, the weight of which thus appears to be greater than it actually is. Again, a certain amount of purpurogallin, which is not quite insoluble in water is lost in the original filtrate and in the washings and is not accounted for. Moreover, according to the method of Willstätter and his co-workers, the reaction is not allowed to proceed to completion but the oxidation is inhibited after a definite interval, usually 10 minutes by the addition of 2N-HCl. Apart from the changes caused by the introduction of the acid and its probable solvent action on the purpurogallin (*cf.* Table III) it should be noted that the velocities of oxidation by a peroxidase may differ widely in different plants so that the values obtained by this method may not convey an accurate idea of the relative peroxidase contents of these plants. Thus Rice and Hanzawa (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1922, 14, 201), who applied this method to the determination of the peroxidase in milk, found that the reaction took seven days to complete, while in the case of an extract of beet-root, the reaction was found by Bach and Chodat (*loc. cit.*) to be completed in less than 24 hours.

In the present paper a method is described which appears to be quite accurate, and should enable a better comparison being made of the peroxidase contents of different plants. It is based on the

interesting observation which was made sometimes ago that when a peroxidase solution containing hydrogen peroxide was treated with an excess of a concentrated aqueous solution of hydroquinone, the latter was quantitatively converted into quinhydrone which separated out as shining needles. It has now been found possible to estimate the quinhydrone formed in this reaction either by a gravimetric or a volumetric process, the latter being preferred both for its simplicity and accuracy.

The experiments described below have been carried out mainly with the common Indian vegetable 'Jhinga' (*Luffa acutangula*, N.O. *Cucurbitaceæ*), and plant saps referred to in various places should be understood to be derived only from this source.

Preparation of Plant Sap.—The fresh fruit, not quite ripe, is cut into thin slices and packed in a stoppered bottle which is placed in a mixture of ice and salt in a glass jar covered with felt and kept at about -8° for 12 hours. The bottle is then opened, the frozen mass transferred to a hand-screw-press (Lautenschlager), the parts of the press coming into direct contact with the sap being made entirely of porcelain. The sap is expressed as completely as possible by applying heavy pressure, an average fruit weighing 250 grams yielding 40-45 c.c. of the sap. The turbid sap is centrifuged (3000 revolution per minute) to free it completely from suspended matter, quickly filtered through glass wool into a 4 oz. stoppered bottle, 3 to 4 drops of toluene are added, and the whole kept in the refrigerator at 0° to 5° . The activity of the enzyme was not found to be appreciably impaired even after a week.

Precipitation of Quinhydrone.—10 C. c. of the clear sap are treated with the same volume of a saturated solution of hydroquinone (4 per cent. approximately), 5 to 10 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide (1 per cent. approximately) are added, and the whole kept in a bath at a temperature of 5° to 10° . During the first ten minutes the liquid remained perfectly clear, and then fine needles of a dark green colour with a bronze-like lusture began to be deposited, the liquid becoming filled with a mass of these crystals at the end of an hour. The crystals were very pure, melted sharply at 171° (correct melting point of quinhydrone is 171°), and gave off the pungent odour of quinone on heating.

Certain interesting results were obtained in the course of the preliminary experiments which were made with a view to obtain standard conditions for the precipitation of quinhydrone by these enzymes.

They showed that any considerable dilution of the reaction mixture with water served to inhibit the oxidation. Thus, on mixing the plant sap (10 c.c.) with freshly boiled water (30 c.c.), and then adding the saturated hydroquinone and 1% hydrogen peroxide solution, and maintaining the whole solution at 10°, no quinhydrone had separated even after 6 hours. On keeping overnight, a small amount of dark precipitate was found to have formed, which, on examination, proved to be mostly insoluble matter mixed with only a small quantity of quinhydrone. Similarly, by varying the amounts of saturated hydroquinone solution, while the volumes of plant sap and H₂O₂ were kept constant, it was found that there was a minimum below which the precipitation of the quinhydrone was incomplete. The results of some of these experiments are shown in Tables I and II.

Estimation of Quinhydrone.—The main objection to gravimetric methods of estimating quinhydrone lies in the difficulty of drying the precipitate. At 100°, it rapidly loses weight due to the volatilisation of the quinone component, and although the weight becomes nearly constant on drying at the laboratory temperature in an evacuated desiccator over sulphuric acid, it takes more than 48 hours for the process to complete. The results which are given in Table III, and which are fairly concordant, were obtained by the following method. The mixture of plant sap (10 c.c.), freshly prepared saturated hydroquinone (10 c.c.) and 1 per cent. hydrogen peroxide (10 c.c.) are kept and stirred in a bath at 10° until the reaction is complete, and no further precipitation takes place (1½ to 2 hours). The whole is then filtered through an Allihn tube fitted with a small perforated disc having a layer of coarse asbestos below and a layer of Gooch asbestos above, to a total height of about 5 mm. The precipitate is washed at first with cold 2% hydroquinone solution and then with ice cold distilled water (5—8 c.c.), the total volume of the wash water as well as that of the reaction mixture being noted for applying a correction for the amount of quinhydrone remaining in solution in the filtrate. For this purpose blank experiments are carried out using the same volumes of plant sap, hydroquinone solution and wash liquid, and a volume of distilled water corresponding to the volume of hydrogen peroxide used. A known weight of quinhydrone in excess of that required to form a saturated solution is now added, the mixture kept at 10° for 1½ to 2 hours, and the quinhydrone filtered, dried and weighed under the same conditions, as before. The difference between the weight of

quinhydrone taken originally and that found after the experiment gives the correction to be applied. After the weight of the Allihn tube has become constant, quinhydrone is dissolved out completely with a small amount of absolute alcohol, and the tube again dried and weighed. In this way, a certain amount of insoluble matter is generally found to have been present which added to the weight of the quinhydrone. The corrections to be applied on account of this insoluble matter are shown in Tables IV and V.

The gravimetric method though not inaccurate involves the application of a number of corrections, and on account of these difficulties, it was later discarded in favour of a volumetric process which gave accurate results in a much shorter time. It is based on the method described by Valeur (*Compt. rend.*, 1899, 129, 552) which was applied originally to benzoquinone and subsequently to quinhydrone itself by Luther and Leubner (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1912, 85, 314) in connection with their measurements of the dissociation constant of quinhydrone. The precipitation and filtration of the quinhydrone is carried out in exactly the same way as in the gravimetric method; the precipitate is then quickly dissolved in alcohol (10 c. c.) and the asbestos in the Allihn tube washed successively with 3 or 4 portions of 5 c. c. alcohol until the filtrate is colourless. A mixture of alcohol (20 c. c. of 95 per cent.), concentrated hydrochloric acid, (20 c. c.) and potassium iodide solution (20 c. c. of 10 per cent.) is now added to the filtrate contained in a stoppered flask immersed in ice water, and the liberated iodine titrated immediately with decinormal sodium thiosulphate and starch.

The results which are given in Tables IV onwards show remarkable concordance.

TABLE I.
(*Preliminary Experiments*).

Effect of adding varying amounts of freshly boiled distilled water to the mixture of sap, hydroquinone and hydrogen peroxide solutions the volumes of which are kept constant at 10°. It shows that any dilution with water should be avoided.

Vol. of hydroquinone (saturated) = 10 c. c. Vol. of 1% H_2O_2 = 10 c. c.
Vol. of sap = 10 c. c.

Expt.	Vol. of water.	Results.
A	50 c. c.	A reddish-brown precipitate small in quantity appears after 24 hours. It is mostly insoluble in alcohol, and liberates very little iodine from KI.

Expt.	Vol. of water.	Results.
B	30 c.c.	Amorphous precipitate formed after six hours; the proportion of quinhydrone is increased.
C	15	Precipitate is crystalline and appears in 2 hours; it is still very impure, and the solid has no sharp melting point.
D	0	Crystals (m.p. 170—71°) appear in 10 minutes and the reaction is completed in an hour.

TABLE II.

Sap A.—The effect of simultaneous variation in the concentration of hydrogen peroxide and hydroquinone on the total yield of quinhydrone. There is a limiting value for the concentration of hydroquinone below which the oxidation appears to be incomplete (*vide* Expts. *g*, *h*, and *i*).

Sap = 10 c.c.

Expt.	Vol. of hydroquinone.	Vol. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Time.	Wt. of quinhydrone.
<i>a</i>	12 c.c.	12 c.c.	1½ hours	0.1572 g.
<i>b</i>	10	10	„	0.1584
<i>c</i>	9	9	„	0.1554
<i>d</i>	9	9	„	0.1568
<i>e</i>	9	9	„	0.1526
<i>f</i>	8	8	„	0.1534
<i>g</i>	6	6	„	0.1400
<i>h</i>	5	5	„	0.1316
<i>i</i>	4	4	18 hours	0.0703

TABLE III.

Sap B.—The effect of adding 2 c.c. 2*N*-HCl for inhibiting the reaction according to Willstätter's method. The yield of the quinhydrone is considerably diminished probably on account of its greater

solubility in a mixture which is approximately 0.05N—acid (*vide* Experiments *d* and *e*).

Hydroquinone = 10 c.c. H₂O₂ = 9 c.c. Sap = 10 c.c.

Expt.	Time.	Vol. of 2N-HCl added.	Wt. of quinhydrone.
<i>a</i>	1½ hours	nil.	0.1484 g.
<i>b</i>	2 hours.	„	0.1480
<i>c</i>	„	„	0.1460
<i>d</i>	„	2 c.c.	0.1303
<i>e</i>	„	„	0.1295

TABLE IV.

Sap C.—Column 2 shows the correction to be applied for the insoluble matter which is always carried down with the quinhydrone in gravimetric estimations. Experiments *c* and *d* show that the values obtained for the weight of quinhydrone by volumetric methods are greater, when carried out directly, than if it were done after drying the precipitate.

Hydroquinone = 10 c.c. H₂O₂ = 10 c.c. Sap = 10 c.c. Time = 1 hr.

Expt.	1	2	3	4
Expt.	Wt. of quinhydrone (gravimetric).	Insol. matter.	Corrected weight of quinhydrone.	Wt. of quinhydrone (volumetric).
<i>a</i>	0.2308 g.	0.0026 g.	0.2282 g.	0.2208 g.
<i>b</i>	0.2272	0.0025	0.2247	0.2188
<i>c</i>	—	—	—	0.2215
<i>d</i>	—	—	—	0.2218

TABLE V.

Sap D.—The experiments are the same as in Table IV, excepting that the precipitates were dried at 50° for the gravimetric estimations. The difference, already noticed in Table IV, between the volumetric results when carried out directly, and those obtained after

drying the precipitate, is found to have greatly increased now. It is therefore obviously due to the loss of quinhydrone involved in drying the precipitate which seems to be unavoidable even at the ordinary temperature.

Volumes of hydroquinone, H_2O_2 and sap = 10 c.c. each ; Time = 1 hour.

Expt.	Wt. of Qh. * dried at 50°.	Insol. water.	Correted wt. of Qh.	Wt. of Qh. (volumetric).	Wt. of quinone corresponding to Qh.
a	0.1738 g.	0.0010 g.	0.1728 g.	0.1715 g.	0.08494 g.
b	0.1734	0.0010	0.1724	0.1703	0.08433
c	—	—	—	0.0778	0.08808
d	—	—	—	0.1768	0.08758

* Qh. = Quinhydrone.

TABLE VI.

Saps F and G.—Column 2 shows the correction to be applied for the amount of quinhydrone held in solution in order to arrive at the absolute weight of this substance formed. The concordance of the results is striking.

Volumes of hydroquinone, H_2O_2 and sap = 10 c.c. each ; Time 1 hour.

(*Sap F*)

	1	2	3	4
Expt.	Wt. of Qh. (volumetric).	Qh. in soln.	True wt. of Qh.	True wt. of quinone.
a	0.1161 g.	0.0215 g.	0.1376 g.	0.06816 g.
b	0.1161	0.0215	0.1376	0.06816
c	0.1162	0.0214	0.1376	0.06816
(<i>Sap G</i>)				
d	0.0721	0.0230	0.0951	0.0471
e	0.0721	0.0230	0.0951	0.0471

TABLE VII.

Sap H.—Effect of increasing the concentration of H_2O_2 on the yield of quinhydrone. Enzyme activity appears to diminish with

increasing concentration of this reagent. Willstätter (*Annalen*, 1926, 449, 154) has made a similar observation in connection with the activity of the peroxidase of beet-root.

Expt.	Hydroquinone = 10 c.c.			Sap = 10 c.c.	
	H ₂ O ₂ .	Wt. of Qh.	Correction.	Total wt.	Wt. of quinone corresponding to Qh.
<i>a</i>	10 c.c. (1%)	0.3796 g.	0.0217 g.	0.4013 g.	0.1987 g.
<i>b</i>	"	0.3781	"	0.3998	0.1981
<i>c</i>	10 c.c. (2%)	0.2150	"	0.2367	0.1172
<i>d</i>	"	0.2150	"	0.2367	0.1172

TABLE VIII.

Sap I.—A second series of experiments confirming the results set forth in Table VII and leading to the conclusion that the use of a stronger solution of H₂O₂ than 1 per cent. is inadvisable.

Hydroquinone = 10 c.c.; Sap = 10 c.c.; Total vol. = 38 c.c.

Expt.	H ₂ O ₂ .	Vol. of wash liquid.	Qh.	Correc-tion.	Total Qh.	Quinone equi-valent.
<i>a</i>	10 c.c. (1%)	8 c.c. of 2% Hq. and water.	0.2311 g.	0.0285 g.	0.2596 g.	0.1286 g.
<i>b</i>	"	"	0.2313	"	0.2596	0.1286
<i>c</i>	" (2%)	"	0.1161	"	0.1446	0.07162
<i>d</i>	" (2%)	"	0.1163	"	0.1448	0.07173

Experiments on the estimations of peroxidases in other plant saps and on the preparations of the pure enzymes are in progress.

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